

Home-School Partnership of Communication and Cultural Sensitivity as Predictors of Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated home-school partnership of communication and cultural sensitivity as predictors of Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study design was correlational, the population was 5,833 teachers in the 320 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State with a sample of 400 teachers, selected using Taro Yamane Mathematical Technique and the stratified sampling technique. The instruments for the study were two scales. These were the validated 'Home-School Partnership of Communication and Cultural Sensitivity Scale' (HSPCCSS) and 'Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment Scale' (SDG4AS) with reliability coefficients of 0.86 and 0.87 respectively. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 alpha level. The findings revealed that home-school partnership of communication predicts the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent by 71%, while cultural sensitivity predicts the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 2%. The study concluded that home-school partnership of communication significantly predicts the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, while cultural sensitivity does not significantly predict the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that school administrators, other school members, and parents should continuously adopt appropriate communication strategies and also embrace and introduce students to cross-cultural values, norms, and practices that can aid students' instruction and well-being towards the attainment of SDG4.

Keywords: Home-School, Partnership, Communication, Cultural Sensitivity, Sustainable Development Goal 4.

INTRODUCTION

Principals, teachers, parents, and guardians of secondary school students are expected to be actively involved in the day-to-day school activities, and programs of the students to attain SDG4, this involvement will cut across supervision, support, instruction, and guidance from all parties involved. However, a ladder to this process will be through home-school partnerships. In this 21st century of technological advancement, there is a need to transform education into a social repositioning by striking a balance between traditional academic pursuits and the development of practical skills.

In the views of Komal and Sarika (2019), a partnership is a much more complex endeavour than merely involvement or participation: it is mutually determined and has benefits for all partners – students, parents, and teachers. This implies that the sphere of influence that exists should be two-way: schools can recognise and celebrate each child’s individuality and welcome all families while helping families recognise their children as students and reinforce the importance of homework and activities that build students’ thinking and skills. This is possible through effective home-school partnerships in a variety of areas such as; communication and cultural sensitivity.

In the view of Wong (2022), home-school partnerships involve a willing and intentional collaboration between the school and family that leads to positive academic and social outcomes. From this definition given, the words ‘willing and intentional’ make it clear what family involvement in school should be in order for it to equal a strong home-school partnership. This is because, while parents or guardians may be interested in developing children’s academic abilities, which involve carrying out activities like attending parent-teacher conferences, revising school work regularly, or volunteering for school activities, these are merely one-way support for the school. It was based on this narrative that Al-hail et al (2021) summed that, a home-school partnership requires a two-way support system where parents and teachers have an open vein of communication to further children’s development. For example, teachers can involve students and their families to share their personal experiences from home. The foregoing as stated by Warhurst (2022), allows teachers to gain a better understanding of students’ social situations and their parents’ points of view, and craft more targeted learning activities. Moreover, students learn better when their significant others like parents and teachers work together to encourage and support them as well as influence how schools are organised (Getha and Febria, 2022). This is because, neither parents nor schools, can address all the developmental needs of a child, thus meaningful involvement of parents and support from the school and community is essential. To support this view, Pepito in Animba (2021) opined that, home-school partnership involves collaborative working relationships between families and schools to support students to become more productive and consistent in work and behaviour which in turn improves their interest, motivation and engagement in learning both at home and in school.

Furthermore, society is becoming more complex, stressful and demanding with neither school nor parents having enough time to establish working relations aimed solely for the good of the student. At the same time, our society has created distinctions about roles that parents and teachers should play in the developmental process in the life of a student. This is because society believes that schools should stick to academics while the home is for moral and emotional development, forgetting that learning about values, integrity, respect, character and relationships starts from the home and is consolidated in the school. Therefore, Principals, teachers, parents, and guardians of secondary school students are expected to be actively involved in the day-to-day school activities, and programs of the students to attain SDG4, this involvement will cut across supervision, support, instruction, communication, and guidance from all parties involved. However, a ladder to this process will be through home-school partnerships of communication and cultural sensitivity.

Additionally, Su-ching (2014) stated that, all experiences students have both in and out of school shape their sense of belonging, what they respect, and care about, feeling of self-worth, competency, understanding of the world around them, beliefs about where they fit into the scheme of things among others. In line with the above, Lerner et al (2022) opined that students learn from observations of adults on how decisions are made, and executed and how problems are solved. Hence the need for home-school partnerships.

From the foregoing, it is glaring that, for sustainable development goal 4 to be achieved, the family through parents/guardians must be actively involved in the education of their children. This is because the family is the most fundamental social unit of all modern societies and it is expected that issues bordering on environment, economy and social issues are discussed and communicated alike. This narrative prompts Animgba (2022) to state that, students/children learn about qualitative education, good sanitation, social equality, a clean environment, peace and the need for a healthy relationship between humans and the environment through a careful lifestyle, which is more obtainable in the family.

Based on the above narrative, Hargraves (2019) posits that, while family engagement and involvement are key to developing strong home-school partnerships, they are not equivalent to partnership. This is because family members may dedicate their time and effort towards their children’s education in ways

of; participating in activities within the school setting such as parent-teacher conferences, volunteer work, attending school functions or field trips, or supporting their child's learning by practising key concepts that involves everyday activities such as laundry and shopping. A partnership between the home and school according to Izuagba et al (2017), is the primary strategy for achieving SDG goals because qualitative education through schools which is primarily determined by homes equips students with knowledge and competencies that increase their productivity, thereby, helping them escape from poverty.

By implication, it is expected that the partnership will bring about economic, social, technological and mindset re-orientation since education is a great equaliser, thereby, reducing crime, strife, and threats to security from discontentment due to disenfranchisement and exclusion. The partnership between the home and the school can lift people out of poverty by helping them understand sustainable and modern methods of farming, nutrition and promotion of life-long opportunities for all. This can increase skills and capacities to use natural resources more sustainably and promote hygiene. When there is an effective partnership between the home and school, students develop the skills required to foster social learning to facilitate, ensure, and promote participation, inclusion and social coherence. ParentKind (2023) summed up that, when parents are involved in their children's education, children do better on a range of measures that includes: useful living, greater self-esteem, higher attendance, lower risk of exclusion, keenness to learning, attainment of satisfactory results, reduced social and professional attainment gap between children and young people from different socio-economic backgrounds.

Communication and Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment:

Communication is derived from the Latin word 'communis', which means 'trying to gain understanding'. Ezeh (2018), defined communication to be the transmission (encoding), receipt and interpretation (decoding) of messages using a specific medium. Communication is one of the essential elements in an institution. Okorie in Newyear (2016), opined that it is the process of transmitting one's thoughts, ideas, wishes, attitudes, and emotions to others.

Communication is central in any institution, and it is the 'live wire' of any given institution, and the source through which the goals and aspirations of any institution can be transmitted. Ejimaji in Ishaka (2017), maintained that communication is the ingredient which makes organisations possible, and the vehicle through which the basic management or administrative functions are carried out. Effective workplace communication according to Ray-offor (2017), is based on interpersonal, professional relationships that are developed through a keen awareness of courtesy, attentive listening, active participation, and appropriate body language.

Suffian, et al (2014), stated that communication plays a key part for leaders in ensuring that people do the right things instead of only doing things in the right way by carefully managing the internal and external relationships in supporting organisational growth. In the views of Mark-Ewa and Nelson (2022), communication in an organisation provides a basis for understanding virtually every human process which occurs in an organisation such as conflict, cooperation, decision-making, the use of power and authority, compliance gaining, resistance, morale and cohesion, and the creation and maintenance of relationships in an organisation.

Communication is simply the transfer of information from one place, person, or group to another. It involves the transmission or exchange of information by speaking, writing, or using other media. Therefore, every communication consists of three parts: the sender, the message, and the receiver. It can be classified into different categories such as: Spoken or oral, non-verbal, written or visual. Obi in Onyali, Ezeugbor, and Okoye (2016), stated that, where effective communication is lacking, the performance of functions may overlap, thereby, causing confusion which will give rise to a waste of time, human, and material resources.

As mentioned by Ogunsanya in Ezeh (2018), for teachers, parents, and students to be highly productive in the school, the school principal has to be dynamic, show good examples, and treat others with dignity, by involving them regularly during discussions and communicating effectively with them using appropriate channels. It is through communication that principals can imbibe in the teachers, parents, and students of expected outcomes, therefore, enhancing the quality of education that can be attained. However, Asodike and Adieme (2015) posit that tasks cannot be accomplished,

objectives cannot be met and decisions cannot be implemented if the school and the home cannot effectively communicate with each other as regards the education of the students.

Based on the above position, Classcraft (2024), summed that, teachers must note that, their ability to communicate with parents helps them to better understand a child's strengths and their individual personality and learning style. Therefore, the more information a teacher has about a student, the more teachers can focus on teaching and being able to address and overcome challenges along the way that may be unique to each child. The receiving end of a home-school partnership is the student, this is because it is the student who benefits the most from the communication between the home and school, and this results in numerous positive advantages.

Conrad (2022), posits that home-school communication enhances the parent-student bond and teacher-student bond by showing students that the adults in their lives care about them and their education. This implies that communication between home and school is an excellent way to teach students good communication skills through modelling how and when to communicate. In the views of Mccutchen (2019), communication between home and school is important not just for teachers and parents but also for the student which aids the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 in schools. The importance of home-school communication is that, through regular interaction with parents, teachers can share information about a student's good work and achievements. Therefore, it is expected that if a student begins to struggle with a certain subject or exhibits behavioural problems, the parent will already have a relationship with the teacher, which helps facilitate parent-teacher collaboration to curb the issue. This cooperative relationship empowers parents to step in and support the student at home, supplementing what the teacher is doing at school.

Benefits of home-school communication

SOE (2020) outlined the benefits of home-school communication to parents, students, and teachers as follows:

- a. **Benefits for Students:** Parents who are more involved in their child's education can help improve academic achievement, this is because, when parents take an interest in school activities, students are given an additional level of accountability. Organising engagement (2023) further opined that, when parents communicate with teachers to discover their children's needs, students see that their family is looking out for them and want them to be successful. In the views of Peter, et al (2022), parents who assist children with homework and remind them to study for tests can increase their chances of short-term and long-term success by helping them develop important habits. Parents can also support children and help boost their confidence by encouraging them when they do well in school.
- b. **Benefits for Parents:** effective parent-teacher communication can also benefit parents. Since parents are not always directly involved in the classroom, regular conversations with teachers can help them understand which subject areas their children are doing well in, and which ones they are not. It can also help them feel valued and more confident in engaging in the learning process (Wong, 2022). To support the foregoing, Murray (2022) summed that, parents who want to be involved can develop a greater role in their child's education by supplementing lessons at home and explaining complicated homework problems for them.
- c. **Benefits for Teachers:** teachers also benefit from parent-teacher communication, as parents can serve as a valuable asset in the learning environment. Murray (2022) affirmed that teachers who cultivate relationships with parents will gain added cooperation, as parents are more likely to work with and reach out to teachers they trust. When parents help their children with homework and behaviour at home, teachers can focus on instruction more effectively in the classroom. Teachers may also see higher rates of homework completion and better grades when parents are involved (Crea, 2015).

Furthermore, Conrad (2022) outlined the advantages of home-school communication to include: improved academic achievement; a positive attitude toward learning; a feeling of empowerment and confidence; enhanced relationships with parents, peers, and teachers; and regular class attendance. It is quite obvious that the benefits of home-school communication cannot be overemphasised, Parent-teacher communication can look different to different teachers and parents. Some relationships may be more difficult to establish than others, but many communication strategies can help teachers and

parents increase engagement in various situations. SOE (2020), enumerated the following as communication strategies for parents and teachers:

- a. Regular in-person communication: This type of communication works greatly for parents who typically drop off and pick up their children from school, this is because such parents have the privilege of meeting with teachers daily.
- b. Parent-teacher conferences: This type of communication is less consistent, but parents and teachers can schedule meetings to discuss a student's work and future goals.
- c. Phone calls/messages and emails: Parents with busy work or personal schedules may not have the opportunity to go to school or schedule conferences. These parents may be easier to reach on the phone or via email. Teachers can also use phone calls and emails to regularly communicate with parents between conferences. Some teachers use mass text messages, WhatsApp, or special messaging apps to communicate with parents.
- d. Open houses: Most schools host annual open houses where parents can visit their children's classrooms. This allows teachers to meet parents for the first time or to meet a second parent who may not be in regular communication with the school. Parent-teacher associations can also be open house events where parents and teachers can establish ongoing relationships through board meetings or PTA meetings in which they help make decisions for the school.
- e. Homework handouts and newsletters: Teachers can create handouts for students to take home that contain information about homework and other tasks. Teachers can also write weekly or monthly newsletters to let parents know what is going on in the classroom and how they can participate.
- f. Class channels/websites: Teachers can create websites, WhatsApp groups or telegram channels for their classes to post announcements, homework, and reminders. This helps ensure that assignments don't get lost in communication between the classroom and home. Other similar methods of communication include social media sites or learning management platforms that will be most convenient for the home and school to use.

Murray (2022) posits that communication between home and school is a key factor in home-school partnership because families need to feel comfortable sharing information about their children's development, while teachers must trust that families will support the academic goals they set for their children. The teacher then becomes an integral part of the partnership because he/she must work closely with the family to ensure that communication remains open and effective (which includes being respectful, kind-hearted, and tolerant).

Cultural Sensitivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4:

Cultural sensitivity is regarded as a necessary ability in today's society; it is also required in any vocation that requires interpersonal interactions across cultures. Moro, Pires, Rita, and Cortez, (2020) summed up that, cultural sensitivity refers to the ability of the school to interpret the meanings of students' feelings and language, both expressed and unexpressed, and to be willing to modify themselves on their desire to compromise to achieve a comfortable environment for both sides. Therefore by implication, cultural sensitivity is an instruction that recognizes the importance of incorporating students' cultural differences into all aspects of learning.

Geeta and Febria (2022), defined cultural sensitivity as a means of being aware of other people's cultural differences and similarities without evaluating them as good or bad. This awareness will enable students who experience different cultures during their education to become more comfortable and confident with their differences later in life. This allows them to interact with a wider range of social groups and makes them more confident in themselves and their interactions with others. This process is in line with the success of SDG4, target 4.6.

Cultural sensitivity is an important concept that is essential in any home-school partnership activity, more important is the fact that Rivers State is a diverse and multicultural State, hence its schools include the world. Cultural sensitivity involves acknowledging and respecting the diverse cultural backgrounds of parents. This acknowledgement is essential in shaping the educational outcomes of children as parents can provide cultural knowledge for the development of their children. The importance of cultural sensitivity in partnerships is that it helps to foster improved communication, respect, and accord between parents, students, and schools.

The 21st Century has been characterised by globalisation, an ongoing process of intensified economic, social, and cultural exchanges. Globalisation is challenging to schools in multiple ways because students in today's classrooms have diverse racial, ethnic, linguistic, socio-economic, gendered, religious, and cultural backgrounds. Therefore, as globalisation continues, students' diversity will continue to increase worldwide, such that teachers and schools face many challenges in providing each student with the same opportunities to achieve his or her potential.

In the view of De Mooij and Hofstede in Baron (2023), cultural sensitivity refers to the quality of being aware of values and belief systems, making decisions, communicating across cultures, and accepting different cultures. This implies that cultural sensitivity refers to the ability to function well in diverse cultures and, it requires interpersonal communication as well as valuing, and respecting variety, and being attentive to cultural variations such as values, beliefs, and behaviours. This cultural understanding allows the home and the school to view the big picture, which improves the partnership process towards the attainment of teaching and learning outcomes.

As stated by Garcia and Pantao (2021), cultural sensitivity is a set of attributes that enables a person to learn about, and relate to individuals who are different from oneself. In a school setting, teachers' cultural sensitivity may help deal with this type. One of the main duties of the school is to be mindful of how students feel, and how much they know about them. Principals and teachers should be culturally sensitive and competent to avoid problems caused by culturally insensitive school management practices. A culturally sensitive person understands that there may be differences between their cultures and that of another person and that these differences may affect their relationship and the way they communicate with each other.

In the views of Moro et al (2020), a culturally sensitive individual would grasp the customs and ways of life of different countries and ethnic groups, or would try to learn and apply new understanding. Important to note is that, culturally sensitive individuals strive to be free of prejudices and preconceived notions of other cultures (Sue in Baron 2023). Additionally, research has shown that culturally sensitive schools change their management methods to support cultural variety and sensitivity (O'Leary et al., 2020). These techniques can be used to build a student-centred partnership that enables the home to participate fully in the school activities that, will in turn, guarantee the students are in a purposeful and secure learning environment. Geeta and Febria (2022) affirmed that, in a culturally sensitive classroom, both students and teachers acknowledge, embrace, appreciate, and capitalise on diversity to enhance the educational process. Everyone, regardless of age, gender, race, religion, financial background, sexual orientation, or political convictions, is encouraged to establish personal connections and master useful intercultural skills. This statement aligns with the provisions of SDG 4 and it can only be achieved through fostering a culturally sensitive learning environment.

Based on the above-stated points, it is worth stating that, the practice of cultural sensitivity between the home and school leads to the attainment of SDG 4, target 4.7 which states that; "By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and appreciation of cultural diversity, and culture's contribution to sustainable development (UNDP 2019)."

A culture of peace and appreciation of cultural diversity can only be obtainable if the home and school are sensitive to individual cultural differences. Therefore the home needs the school as much as the school needs the home for the partnership towards the attainment of SDG 4 to become a reality. In line with the foregoing, UNESCO (2017), described target 4.7 as providing 'learners with the knowledge and competencies they need to make all the SDGs a reality'.

Education plays a fundamental role in the achievement of sustainable development, as it raises awareness of global issues and provides individuals with the essential skills and knowledge to act upon them. Classrooms differ, a regular classroom will not have the same features as that of a culturally sensitive classroom. Based on this narrative, Farinde-Wu, Glover, and Williams (2017) outlined the characteristics of culturally sensitive schools including; creating relationships of trust with parents and students; having the conviction that all students can succeed academically, regardless of their racial or linguistic background; supporting active teaching, which encourages cooperative learning, increasing learners' academic success, motivation, and passion; and including the cultural context in lessons. It is quite obvious that today's world is diverse, and this diversity manifests itself in

a variety of ways, including gender, religion, race, and even cultural affiliation, as a result, various beliefs, points of view, and activities are suggested (Jomarie, 2023).

Therefore, everyone's behaviour, particularly in schools, is distinctive and influenced by their cultural heritage. Tandem to the above, Bonner, et al (2018) posit that today's schools are made up of a variety of cultural, ethnic, religious, and socioeconomic groups, necessitating multicultural education programs that show an understanding and respect for the diversity of children and adolescents. To support this narrative, Rafid and Khotimah (2021) stated that students' opinions in the school environment are influenced by cultural differences in authority, academic, and social values, self-regulatory, peer regulation techniques, and teachers' classroom management strategies.

Statement of the Problem

The success of children's learning and education depends on an effective partnership between home and school. Different research across the globe and especially in Rivers State Nigeria have shown that some parents have little time to supervise, participate, or communicate their children's school activities, and some teachers do not bother to provide feedback to parents or follow up with students learning. With the diverse nature of Rivers State, it is evident that its schools are characterised by students from different ethnic backgrounds, if the students in these schools are not properly trained and nurtured about diverse ethnic backgrounds they will have issues with coping and accepting the diverse nature of their peers in the school. The misalignment of the home and school values creates a considerable strain on the learning of students which can hinder quality education attainment, this strain can be caused due to ineffective communication and a lack of cultural sensitivity or awareness between the home and school. There are several cases of stigmatised cultural practices which are caused by lack of communication and training, this lack hinders the essence of actualizing a culture of peace and developing global citizens according to the SDGs. Addressing this pitfall is therefore paramount towards SDG 4 attainment, which prompted the need for this study.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study investigated home-school partnership of communication and cultural sensitivity as predictors of Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. examine the extent home-school partnership of communication predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the extent home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. To what extent does home-school partnership of communication predict sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity predict Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level:

1. Home-school partnership of communication does not significantly predict sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity does not significantly predict sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was correlational, the population of 5833 teachers from 320 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, out of which 400 teachers were sampled for the study using the Taro Yamane and stratified sampling techniques. The instruments used in collecting data for this study were two scales. These were the validated 'Home-School Partnership of Communication and Cultural Sensitivity Scale' (HSPCCSS) and 'Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment Scale' (SDG4AS) with reliability coefficients of 0.86 and 0.87 obtained using Cronbach Alpha mathematical procedure. Simple regression was used in answering the research questions while t-tests associated with simple regression were used in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1: *To what extent does home-school partnership of communication predict sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent Home-School Partnership of Communication Predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	0.905 ^a	0.711	0.710	71.1%	High Extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent)

Data in Table 1 presents the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent home-school partnership of communication predicts sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State with the model as 1. The regression (R) score value came out as 0.905^a, the regression square (R²) coefficient as 0.711 and the adjusted regression square as 0.710 while the extent of prediction (coefficient of determinism) was calculated to be at 71.1% (0.711 × 100). When reference is made to the decision rule, 71.1% falls between 74% - 50% (High Extent), hence, this suggests that the prediction home-school partnership of communication and Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment is to a high extent. Based on the foregoing observations, the result shows that home-school partnership of communication predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent by 71%.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity predict Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent Home-School Partnership of Cultural Sensitivity Predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Extent of Prediction	Decision
1	0.137 ^a	0.022	0.021	2.2%	Very Low Extent

Decision Rule: 100%- 75% (Very High Extent), 74% - 50% (High Extent), 49%-25% (Low Extent) and 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent).

Data in Table 2, revealed the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity predicts sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State with the model as 1. The regression (R) score value came out as 0.137^a, the regression square (R²) coefficient as 0.022 and the adjusted regression square as 0.021 while the extent of prediction (coefficient of determinism) was calculated to be at 2.2% (0.022 × 100). When reference is made to the decision rule, 2.2% falls between 0% - 24% (Very Low Extent), hence, this suggests that the prediction of home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity and Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment is to a very low extent. Based on the foregoing observations, the result shows that home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 2%.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Home-school partnership of communication does not significantly predict sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3 :Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Home-School Partnership of Communication Significantly Predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	2.951	0.077		38.374	0.000		
Communication	0.104	0.029	0.105	3.587	0.000	0.05	Hypothesis is rejected

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable Development Goal 4

Data in Table 3 presents the summary of t-test associated with simple regression analysis on the prediction of home-school partnership of communication analysis on sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The t-calculated values used in testing the hypothesis was 3.587, while the p-value remained 0.000, with an alpha level of 0.05. At 0.05 alpha level and t-observed value of 3.587, the p-value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05, this suggests a significant prediction of the independent variable (home-school partnership of communication) on the dependent variable (Sustainable Development Goal 4). Based on this premise, the null hypothesis is rejected, by implication, home-school partnership of communication significantly predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: Home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity does not significantly predict sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Home-School Partnership of Cultural Sensitivity Significantly Predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 Attainment in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Alpha level	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	2.599	0.075		34.444	0.000		
Cultural Sensitivity	0.036	0.028	0.037	1.262	0.207	0.05	Hypothesis is accepted

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable Development Goal 4

Data in Table 4 revealed the summary of t-test associated with simple regression analysis on the prediction of home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity analysis on sustainable development goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The t-calculated values used in testing the hypothesis was 1.262, while the p-value remained 0.207, with an alpha level of 0.05. At 0.05 alpha level and t-observed value of 1.262, the p-value of 0.207 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05, this suggests an insignificant prediction of the independent variable (home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity) on the dependent variable (Sustainable Development Goal 4). Based on this premise, the null hypothesis is accepted, by implication, home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity does not significantly predict Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of the study revealed that home-school partnership of communication predicted Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent by 71%. Similarly, the corresponding hypothesis established that home-school partnership of communication significantly predicted Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings corroborate Suffian et al (2014), Asodike and Adieme (2015), Onyali, et al (2016), Ray-offor (2017), Mccutchen (2019), Conrad (2022), Classcraft (2024) whose scholarly works revealed how significant communication could be in promoting the attainment of educational goals such as Sustainable Development Goal 4. Given this, Conrad (2022) asserted that home-school communication enhances the parent-student bond and teacher-student bond by showing students that the adults in their lives care about them and their education. This implies that communication between home and school is an excellent way to teach students good communication skills through modelling how and when to communicate. In the views of Mccutchen (2019), communication between home and school is important not just for teachers and parents but also for the student which aids Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in schools.

The second finding of the study revealed that home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity predicted Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a very low extent by 2%. Also, a corresponding finding from the hypothesis established that home-school partnership of cultural sensitivity does not significantly predict Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings contradict Bonner, et al (2018), UNDP (2019), Rafid and Khotimah (2021), and Jomarie (2023), whose academic contribution publicised that cultural sensitivity helps to foster improved communication, respect, and accord between parents, students, and schools, which result in the attainment of SDG4. To support this narrative, Rafid and Khotimah (2021) stated that students' opinions in the school environment are influenced by cultural differences in authority, academic, social values, self-regulatory, peer regulation techniques, and teachers' classroom management strategies. According to the scholars, when the school and parents fail to address and manage the issue of cultural differences, it becomes difficult for the school to achieve its goals such as quality education delivery. UNDP (2019) observed that a culture of peace and appreciation of cultural diversity can only be obtainable if the home and school are sensitive to individual cultural differences, without which it will be difficult for the school to achieve the targets of SDG4. This could be the reason for the results above. Therefore the home needs the school as much as the school needs the home for the partnership towards the attainment of SDG 4 to become a reality.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that home-school partnership of communication significantly predicts Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. However, home-school partnerships of cultural sensitivity do not significantly predict Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. This is because the prediction of both variables were high and low on Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusion therein, the following recommendations are offered:

1. School administrators and other school members should continuously partner with parents to adopt appropriate communication strategies and skills that should be used in discussions and during students' instruction to guarantee Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment.
2. The school administrators, teachers and parents should work together to create a successful environment that promotes internal cohesion and cultural tolerance. A positive school climate where cross-fertilisation of cultural ideas remains a key to Sustainable Development Goal 4 attainment because a school environment replete with rancour and leg pulling is not a fertile environment for quality education to be nurtured and developed.

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